

Anatomy-Preserving Latent Diffusion for Generation of Brain Segmentation Masks with Ischemic Infarct

1st Lucía Borrego

*Department of Diagnostic Imaging
Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
Barcelona, Spain
lborrego@santpau.cat*

2nd Vajira Thambawita

*SimulaMet
Oslo, Norway
vajira@simula.no*

3rd Marco Ciuffreda

*Department of Diagnostic Imaging
Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
Barcelona, Spain
mciuffreda@santpau.cat*

4th Inés del Val

*Department of Diagnostic Imaging
Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
Barcelona, Spain
idelval@santpau.cat*

5th Alejandro Dominguez

*Department of Medical Physics
Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
Barcelona, Spain
adominguezp@santpau.cat*

6th Josep Munuera

*Department of Diagnostic Imaging
Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau
Barcelona, Spain
jmunuera@santpau.cat*

Abstract—The scarcity of high-quality segmentation masks remains a major bottleneck for medical image analysis, particularly in non-contrast CT (NCCT) neuroimaging, where manual annotation is costly and variable. To address this limitation, we propose an anatomy-preserving generative framework for the unconditional synthesis of multi-class brain segmentation masks, including ischemic infarcts.

The proposed approach combines a variational autoencoder trained exclusively on segmentation masks to learn an anatomical latent representation, with a diffusion model operating in this latent space to generate new samples from pure noise. At inference, synthetic masks are obtained by decoding denoised latent vectors through the frozen VAE decoder, with optional coarse control over lesion presence via a binary prompt.

Qualitative results show that the generated masks preserve global brain anatomy, discrete tissue semantics, and realistic variability, while avoiding the structural artifacts commonly observed in pixel-space generative models. Quantitative evaluation confirms that latent-space diffusion achieves 7–8× lower FID than a pixel-space baseline, and downstream segmentation experiments demonstrate a +10.7% mean Dice improvement when synthetic masks are used for data augmentation.

Index Terms—Latent diffusion models, anatomy-aware generative modeling, brain segmentation masks, ischemic infarct, non-contrast CT (NCCT), medical image synthesis

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning has become the dominant paradigm in medical image analysis, achieving state-of-the-art performance in tasks such as segmentation, detection, and disease characterization. However, supervised methods critically depend on the availability of large, diverse, and well-annotated datasets. In neuroimaging, and particularly in non-contrast computed tomography (NCCT), acquiring high-quality pixel-level annotations is especially challenging due to the need for expert neuroradiological knowledge, the time-consuming nature of manual annotation, and inter-observer variability. In addition,

privacy regulations and institutional constraints often limit data sharing across centers, further exacerbating data scarcity [1].

To address these limitations, synthetic data generation has emerged as a promising strategy for dataset augmentation and improved generalization. Early approaches predominantly relied on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), which have been widely applied to medical image synthesis and segmentation-related tasks, including mask-conditioned image synthesis and joint image–mask generation. Despite their success, GAN-based methods suffer from well-known limitations such as training instability, mode collapse, and limited diversity, particularly when modeling complex anatomical structures and multi-class spatial relationships [2].

Beyond image synthesis, several works have explored the direct generation of segmentation masks to model anatomical variability, including shape-based statistical models, variational autoencoders (VAEs), and GAN-based mask generators. While these approaches can capture coarse anatomical structure, they often struggle to preserve fine-grained spatial coherence and realistic inter-class relationships, especially in high-resolution, multi-tissue brain segmentation tasks [4]. Moreover, many methods rely on paired image–mask data or strong shape assumptions, which limits their scalability.

Diffusion probabilistic models (DPMs) have recently emerged as a more stable and expressive alternative to GANs, demonstrating superior sample quality and diversity in both natural and medical image synthesis. Recent studies have applied diffusion models to medical image generation, conditional synthesis, and joint image–mask generation [3], [4]. However, only a limited number of works have explored the unconditional generation of segmentation masks using diffusion models. These approaches typically operate in pixel space and often produce anatomically implausible results,

such as fragmented regions or broken topology, particularly in multi-class settings [5], [9], [10].

In this work, we address the underexplored problem of unconditional generation of anatomically coherent brain tissue segmentation masks for NCCT. Instead of performing diffusion in pixel space, we propose an anatomy-preserving latent diffusion framework in which diffusion is carried out in the latent space of a VAE trained exclusively on segmentation masks. The VAE learns a compact latent manifold that encodes global anatomical structure and inter-tissue relationships, acting as a strong anatomical prior. A diffusion model is then trained in this latent space to generate diverse and realistic segmentation masks from pure Gaussian noise [6].

By decoupling anatomical structure learning from stochastic generation, the proposed approach reduces the structural artifacts commonly observed in pixel-space diffusion models and eliminates the need for conditioning inputs or paired image-mask data at inference time. As a downstream application, the generated masks can be used as structural inputs for a SPADE-based¹ image synthesis framework to generate corresponding NCCT images. Nevertheless, the primary focus of this work is the mask generation pipeline itself.

In summary, this work introduces a simple and effective framework for the unconditional synthesis of anatomically coherent brain segmentation masks. By combining an explicit anatomical latent prior with latent diffusion, the proposed approach bridges classical shape modeling and modern diffusion-based generation, making it suitable for scalable dataset augmentation in annotation-scarce medical imaging scenarios.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We propose an anatomy-preserving latent diffusion framework for the unconditional generation of multi-class brain segmentation masks from non-contrast CT data, including ischemic infarct regions, and illustrate its generative capabilities through an interactive model demonstration.
- We introduce a mask-only variational autoencoder that learns an explicit anatomical latent space, constraining the generation process to anatomically plausible configurations without requiring conditioning images at inference time.
- We provide quantitative validation through a pixel-space baseline comparison (7–8× FID improvement) and a downstream segmentation experiment (+10.7% mean Dice), and release a publicly available synthetic dataset of 605 multi-class segmentation masks together with pre-trained models and generation scripts.

II. DATASET AND METHODS

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

The dataset used in this study consists of non-contrast computed tomography (NCCT) brain scans acquired from 86 patients diagnosed with ischemic stroke of cardioembolic

(a) Inferior cervical slice (discarded). (b) Skull base (discarded). (c) Supratentorial brain slice (retained).

Fig. 1: Illustration of the slice selection strategy used in this study.

origin, according to the TOAST (Trial of ORG 10172 in Acute Stroke Treatment) classification criteria. Restricting the cohort to a single etiological subtype was a deliberate choice aimed at reducing heterogeneity in lesion distribution, vascular territory involvement, and underlying pathophysiological mechanisms.

Only NCCT scans acquired during the post-acute phase, defined as 24 to 48 hours after symptom onset, were included. This temporal window was selected for several reasons. First, hyperacute NCCT scans often exhibit subtle or absent parenchymal changes, leading to increased variability and uncertainty in tissue delineation. Second, scans acquired beyond the early post-acute phase may present secondary effects such as edema resorption or structural deformation, which introduce additional variability unrelated to the primary tissue composition.

All scans were collected retrospectively as part of routine clinical care at Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau (Barcelona, Spain). Data were acquired using standard clinical NCCT scanners and were fully anonymized prior to processing, in accordance with institutional review board approval and local ethical guidelines.

To ensure anatomical consistency and exclude irrelevant structures, a standardized slice selection strategy was applied to all NCCT volumes. Axial slices were retained only within a restricted cranial range corresponding to 20%–95% of the total cranial height. This strategy was designed to systematically remove slices dominated by non-brain anatomy, including:

- Cervical and upper neck structures.
- The skull base and posterior fossa.
- Slices containing large proportions of extracranial tissue or severe imaging artifacts.

By discarding the inferior and extreme superior portions of the head, the resulting dataset focuses exclusively on supratentorial brain anatomy, which is most relevant for ischemic stroke analysis and downstream modeling tasks. This selection also reduces anatomical variability unrelated to cerebral tissue organization, facilitating more stable and consistent learning of structural patterns by the generative model.

Following patient-level and slice-level selection, a total of approximately 6,500 axial slices were retained across the 86 patients.

¹<https://github.com/NVlabs/SPADE>

Fig. 2: Example of multi-class tissue segmentation on a representative NCCT slice. CTseg was used to automatically segment normal tissue classes, whereas ischemic infarct regions correspond to manual annotations provided by expert annotators.

B. Annotation Protocol and Multi-class Mask Construction

Ischemic infarct regions were manually segmented by two radiology residents and reviewed by two board-certified neuroradiologists; disagreements were resolved by consensus. Normal tissue labels were obtained using CTseg² [8], a deep learning framework for multi-class tissue segmentation in NCCT, producing background, CSF, skull/bone, and brain parenchyma maps (Fig. 2). Final multi-class masks ($C = 7$) were created by merging infarct annotations with CTseg outputs, with infarct labels taking precedence in overlapping regions.

Across the 86-patient cohort, 38 (44.2%) presented at least one ischemic lesion and 48 (55.8%) showed no visible lesions; 13 (15.1%) presented more than one lesion. Acute and chronic infarcts were merged into a single infarct class without temporal differentiation.

C. Preprocessing and Encoding

All masks were resized to a fixed spatial resolution of 256×256 pixels using nearest-neighbor interpolation, preserving discrete boundaries and preventing label mixing. Each mask was converted from a single-channel label map into a one-hot tensor $X \in \{0, 1\}^{C \times H \times W}$ to enable categorical reconstruction losses during training. Color palettes were used exclusively for the visualization of qualitative results (Figure 2; all training was performed in label space.

D. Data Split and Training Usage

Data were split at the patient level to prevent slice-level leakage across subjects. A total of 61 patients were assigned to the training set, 8 to the validation set, and 7 to the test set.

At the slice level, the training, validation, and test sets comprised 5,238, 660, and 609 axial slices, respectively. The training set was used to fit the generative models, the validation set to monitor training stability and select checkpoints, and the test set was held out for qualitative evaluation only.

²<https://github.com/WCHN/CTseg>

The test set was held out for qualitative evaluation; downstream segmentation experiments are described in Section IV-D

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Design Rationale and Problem Formulation

The proposed framework decouples anatomical structure learning from stochastic generation through two stages: (1) a VAE trained exclusively on masks learns a compact anatomical latent manifold; (2) a diffusion model operates in this space to sample novel configurations from Gaussian noise. This design avoids the fragmented regions and label inconsistencies commonly observed in pixel-space diffusion of discrete anatomical labels [5], [9], [10], as confirmed experimentally in Section IV-C.

Let $x \in \{0, \dots, C - 1\}^{H \times W}$ be a discrete multi-class segmentation mask with $C = 7$ classes and $H = W = 256$. Its one-hot representation is $X \in \{0, 1\}^{C \times H \times W}$. Each training mask is assigned a binary prompt $y \in \{0, 1\}$ indicating infarct absence/presence, enabling sampling from $p_\theta(x | y)$ without spatial conditioning. An overview of the framework is shown in Fig. 3.

B. Stage I: MaskVAE as an Anatomical Prior

Directly generating discrete multi-class masks in pixel space is challenging because anatomical masks contain sharp boundaries, topology constraints, and strong long-range dependencies (e.g., skull enclosing brain, CSF surrounding parenchyma). To constrain generation to anatomically plausible configurations, we first learn an explicit anatomical prior via a variational autoencoder (VAE) trained exclusively on segmentation masks.

1) *Architecture*: The MaskVAE encoder E_ϕ maps one-hot masks X to the parameters of a diagonal Gaussian posterior distribution:

$$(\mu, \log \sigma^2) = E_\phi(X), \quad (1)$$

where $\mu, \sigma \in \mathbb{R}^D$ and $D = 256$ is the latent dimension. The encoder consists of four strided convolution blocks with kernel size 4, stride 2 and ReLU activations, producing a compact feature representation of size $256 \times 16 \times 16$, which is flattened and projected into $(\mu, \log \sigma^2)$.

A latent vector is sampled using the reparameterization trick:

$$z = \mu + \sigma \odot \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I). \quad (2)$$

The decoder G_ϕ maps z back to mask logits $\hat{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times H \times W}$:

$$\hat{L} = G_\phi(z). \quad (3)$$

The final discrete reconstruction is obtained by $\hat{x} = \arg \max_c \hat{L}_c$.

2) *Training Objective*: Reconstruction is treated as pixel-wise multi-class classification. Compared to regression losses (e.g., MSE), a categorical cross-entropy loss preserves discrete semantics and avoids blurred or mixed labels:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} = \text{CE}(\hat{L}, x). \quad (4)$$

To regularize the latent distribution toward a standard normal prior and encourage a smooth latent manifold, we include a Kullback–Leibler divergence term:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} = D_{\text{KL}}(q_\phi(z | X) \| \mathcal{N}(0, I)). \quad (5)$$

The final VAE objective is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}, \quad (6)$$

where β controls the strength of regularization ($\beta = 0.01$ in our implementation).

3) *Lesion-aware Sampling for Imbalanced Data*: Infarct pixels are rare compared to normal tissue and background. To ensure that the VAE latent space captures pathological configurations, we apply a weighted sampling strategy during VAE training. Each slice receives a sampling weight w_i defined as:

$$w_i = \begin{cases} 5, & \text{if } \exists (u, v) \text{ such that } x_i(u, v) = \text{lesion}, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

A weighted random sampler draws training batches with replacement according to $\{w_i\}$, increasing the frequency of lesion-containing masks while keeping the loss function unchanged.

C. Stage II: Promptable Latent Diffusion

After training, the VAE is frozen and used as a fixed anatomical decoder. We then learn a diffusion model in the latent space to sample novel latent codes that remain compatible with the anatomical manifold learned by the VAE.

1) *Forward Diffusion Process in Latent Space*: For each training mask, we sample $z_0 \sim q_\phi(z | X)$. We then draw a timestep $t \sim \mathcal{U}\{0, \dots, T-1\}$ and generate a noisy latent vector:

$$z_t = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} z_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon, \quad \epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{i=0}^t (1 - \beta_i)$ is the cumulative product of $(1 - \beta_i)$ and $\{\beta_i\}$ follows a linear schedule. In our implementation, diffusion is performed with $T = 100$ timesteps to balance sampling efficiency and mask fidelity.

2) *Prompt Encoding and Conditioning*: Each slice is assigned a binary prompt $y \in \{0, 1\}$ indicating lesion absence/presence. A learnable embedding table maps y to a vector $p(y) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_p}$ with $d_p = 16$:

$$p(y) = \text{Embed}(y). \quad (9)$$

Conditioning is implemented by concatenation (rather than cross-attention), which is sufficient for a binary control signal and yields a lightweight denoiser. The denoiser input is:

$$\text{inp} = [z_t; t/T; p(y)]. \quad (10)$$

Fig. 3: Overview of the proposed anatomy-preserving latent diffusion framework for synthetic brain mask generation using a frozen MaskVAE decoder and latent diffusion.

3) *Denoising Network and Objective*: We train a neural network ϵ_θ to predict the injected noise:

$$\hat{\epsilon} = \epsilon_\theta(z_t, t, p(y)). \quad (11)$$

The diffusion model is trained with a mean squared error loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{diff}} = \mathbb{E} [\|\hat{\epsilon} - \epsilon\|_2^2]. \quad (12)$$

In practice, ϵ_θ is implemented as an MLP with two hidden layers of width 1024 and SiLU activations, mapping from \mathbb{R}^{D+1+d_p} to \mathbb{R}^D .

4) *Reverse Process and Mask Generation*: At inference, we initialize $z_T \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ and iteratively apply the reverse denoising updates from $t = T-1$ down to 0 to obtain z_0 . The final mask logits are produced by the frozen VAE decoder:

$$\hat{L} = G_\phi(z_0), \quad (13)$$

and the discrete synthetic mask is obtained by pixel-wise argmax:

$$\tilde{x}(u, v) = \arg \max_c \hat{L}_c(u, v). \quad (14)$$

This yields anatomically coherent multi-class segmentation masks directly from noise, with optional lesion control via the prompt variable y .

IV. RESULTS

A. Qualitative Mask Generation

Figure 4 shows representative examples of real and synthetic brain segmentation masks generated by the proposed framework. The top row corresponds to samples generated without lesion conditioning ($y = 0$), while the bottom row shows samples generated with lesion conditioning ($y = 1$). - Across both settings, synthetic masks preserve global brain anatomy, clear tissue boundaries, and consistent class semantics comparable to real data. When lesion conditioning is enabled, ischemic infarct regions are generated without disrupting the overall anatomical structure.

Top row: Real masks

Bottom row: Synthetic masks

Fig. 4: Qualitative comparison between real (top row) and synthetic (bottom row) brain segmentation masks generated without lesion conditioning ($y = 0$, left) and with lesion conditioning ($y = 1$, right).

Fig. 5: Pixel-wise class distribution: real vs. synthetic masks for lesion-free ($y = 0$) and lesion-conditioned ($y = 1$) settings.

B. Class Distribution Analysis

Figure 5 summarizes pixel-wise class distributions across real and synthetic masks for both conditioning settings (500 samples each). Synthetic data closely match real class proportions across all tissue classes. In lesion-conditioned samples, infarct pixel prevalence is comparable between real and synthetic masks (1.58% vs. 1.49%), with minor parenchymal redistributions consistent with infarcted tissue replacing healthy regions. Binary conditioning naturally yields variability in lesion extent without explicit size constraints.

C. Pixel-Space Baseline Comparison

To justify latent-space diffusion, we trained a pixel-space MLP baseline operating directly on flattened one-hot masks without the VAE, under identical conditions ($T=100$, same epochs, same MLP architecture). FID was computed using Inception-v3 features on color-encoded masks. As shown in Table I, the proposed method achieves 7–8 \times lower FID, confirming that the anatomical latent prior is essential for structural coherence.

Qualitatively, pixel-space samples exhibit random label mixing and absence of global anatomical organization, in contrast

TABLE I: FID comparison: proposed latent diffusion vs. pixel-space MLP baseline (500 samples per setting, Inception-v3 features).

Method	FID ($y=0$)	FID ($y=1$)
Pixel-space MLP	264.42	230.94
Proposed	78.74	64.53

TABLE II: FID at selected training epochs (proposed model).

Checkpoint	FID
Epoch 100	64.43
Epoch 400	63.91
Epoch 800	61.88

to the proposed method which preserves tissue topology and inter-class relationships.

FID was also monitored across training epochs to select the final checkpoint (Table II). The lowest value was obtained at epoch 800.

D. Downstream Segmentation Evaluation

To assess the practical utility of the generated masks, we conducted a segmentation experiment using a U-Net++ model with a ResNet-34 encoder trained under three configurations on real NCCT data. As summarized in Table III, augmenting real training data with 1,000 synthetic mask-image pairs (masks from our model; images generated with SegGuidedDiff [9]) improved mean Dice by +10.7% over the real-only baseline. Notably, a model trained exclusively on synthetic data achieved a mean Dice of 0.6575, surpassing the real-data baseline (0.6233), demonstrating that the generated masks convey sufficient anatomical and pathological variability for standalone use. The largest improvements were observed for white matter (+60.6%, $p < 0.001$) and ischemic infarct (+60.2%). Figure 6 shows representative cases where the augmented model produces predictions visually closer to the ground truth.

V. DISCUSSION

By decoupling anatomical representation learning from stochastic generation, the proposed framework enables stable synthesis of anatomically plausible masks directly from noise. Constraining diffusion to the VAE latent space enforces global anatomical consistency and prevents structurally implausible configurations, as quantitatively confirmed by the 7–8 \times FID improvement over the pixel-space baseline. The binary lesion prompt provides effective semantic control while maintaining anatomical coherence and natural variability in lesion extent.

Downstream segmentation experiments further confirm practical utility: augmenting real training data with synthetic mask-image pairs improved mean Dice by +10.7%, and a model trained exclusively on synthetic data surpassed the real-data baseline (0.6575 vs. 0.6233), demonstrating that the generated masks capture sufficient anatomical and pathological variability for use in low-resource settings.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The framework operates on independent 2D slices without enforcing

TABLE III: Downstream segmentation Dice on real test set (UNet++, ResNet-34 encoder). Real: trained on real data only. Synth-only: trained on synthetic data only. Augmented: real + synthetic.

Class	Real	Synth-only	Augmented
Background	0.9236	0.9742	0.9769
Soft tissue	0.7689	0.8523	0.8609
Bone	0.9057	0.9079	0.9134
CSF	0.6072	0.6413	0.6799
White matter	0.2437	0.3338	0.3915
Gray matter	0.7696	0.7495	0.7750
Ischemic inf.	0.1444	0.1436	0.2314
Mean	0.6233	0.6575	0.6898

Fig. 6: Qualitative segmentation results. Left to right: input CT, ground truth, baseline (real only), augmented (real + synthetic). The augmented model improves delineation of white matter and ischemic infarct.

volumetric consistency, and lesion control is restricted to binary presence or absence. The dataset comprises 86 patients from a single institution and a single stroke etiology (cardioembolic)—a deliberate choice to reduce confounding variability, but one that limits generalizability to broader clinical settings. Extensions to 3D modeling, finer-grained lesion conditioning, and multi-centre validation constitute the primary directions for future work.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We introduced an anatomy-preserving latent diffusion framework for unconditional generation of multi-class brain segmentation masks from NCCT, including ischemic infarct regions. Diffusion in the VAE latent space achieves 7–8× lower FID than a pixel-space baseline, accurately reproduces real class distributions, and improves downstream segmentation by +10.7% mean Dice when used for data augmentation.

A model trained exclusively on synthetic data surpassed the real-data baseline, highlighting the standalone utility of the generated masks. Future work will explore 3D volumetric extensions, structured lesion conditioning, and multi-centre generalizability.

VII. DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

The code used to generate the synthetic segmentation masks is available at https://github.com/lucixia3/synthetic_masks_generation.git, and the resulting dataset is available at https://huggingface.co/datasets/SEARCH-IHI/IISM_brain.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Skandarani, P. M. Jodoin, and A. Lalonde, “GANs for Medical Image Synthesis: An Empirical Study,” *J Imaging*, vol. 9, no. 3, p. 69, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/JIMAGING9030069/S1.
- [2] Z. Usama, A. Alavi, and J. Chan, “A Review on the Applications of GANs for 3D Medical Image Analysis,” *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 15, no. 20, Oct. 2025, doi: 10.3390/APPI52011219/S1.
- [3] R. Macháček *et al.*, “Mask-conditioned latent diffusion for generating gastrointestinal polyp images,” in *Proc. 4th ACM Workshop on Intelligent Cross-Data Analysis and Retrieval (ICDAR)*, joint with ACM Int. Conf. on Multimedia Retrieval (ICMR), pp. 1–9, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1145/3592571.3592978.
- [4] Y. Shi *et al.*, “Diffusion Models for Medical Image Computing: A Survey,” *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, early access, 2024, doi: 10.26599/TST.2024.9010047.
- [5] J. Cai, Z. Zhang, L. Cui, Y. Zheng, and L. Yang, “Towards cross-modal organ translation and segmentation: A cycle- and shape-consistent generative adversarial network,” *Medical Image Analysis*, vol. 52, pp. 174–184, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.media.2018.12.002.
- [6] W. H. L. Pinaya *et al.*, “Brain Imaging Generation with Latent Diffusion Models,” in *Proc. MICCAI, LNCS* vol. 13609, pp. 117–126, 2022, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-18576-2_12.
- [7] R. Rombach, A. Blattmann, D. Lorenz, P. Esser, and B. Ommer, “High-Resolution Image Synthesis with Latent Diffusion Models,” in *Proc. IEEE CVPR*, pp. 10674–10685, 2022, doi: 10.1109/CVPR52688.2022.01042.
- [8] WCHN, “CTseg: Brain CT image segmentation, normalization, skull-stripping and intracranial volume computation,” GitHub repository, accessed Jan. 8, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/WCHN/CTseg>
- [9] N. Konz, Y. Chen, H. Dong, and M. A. Mazurowski, “Anatomically-controllable medical image generation with segmentation-guided diffusion models,” in *Proc. MICCAI, LNCS* vol. 15007, pp. 88–98, 2024, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-72104-5_9.
- [10] A. Bieder *et al.*, “Unconditional generation of medical segmentation masks with denoising diffusion probabilistic models,” in *MICCAI Workshop on Uncertainty for Safe Utilization of Machine Learning in Medical Imaging*, 2023.